

The Influence of Learning Independence and Time Management on The Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students of SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Learning Independence, Time Management, Learning outcomes

Received : 10, August

Revised : 17, September

Accepted: 22, October

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ABSTRACT

ABSTRACT

This research uses a quantitative type of research with a quantitative descriptive data analysis approach. Class VIII students of SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar with a total of 186 students constitute the population in this study. Sampling in this study used the proportional allocation formula technique. Using sampling techniques in this research, there were 127 people consisting of classes VIII-1, VIII-2, VIII-3, VIII-4, VIII-5 and VIII-6. Data collection techniques use questionnaires and documentation. The hypothesis making technique uses multiple linear regression analysis. The results of this study show that: 1) There is a positive and significant influence of learning independence on student learning outcomes, seen from the significance value in the t test results of $0.000 < 0.05$, and the t test where the calculated t value of learning independence is $(3.954) > t$ table (1.65694) which means that this variable is significant. 2) There is a positive and significant influence of time management on student learning outcomes, seen from the t test where the calculated t value of time management is $(3.857) > t$ table (1.65694) which means that this variable is significant. 3) Learning independence and time management together influence learning outcomes, seen from the F test where the calculated F value is $(23.755) > \text{table F value } (3.067)$. The R square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.277, which means that 27.7% of the learning independence and time management variables influence student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 72.3% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research. The regression value is 1920.882, while the residual value is 5013.544, which means there are other factors that influence learning outcomes but were not studied in this study, namely 5013.544. The results of the multiple regression analysis test are $Y = 29.426 + 0.372X_1 + 0.373X_2$, which means that variable X_2 (time management) with a value of 0.373 has a more dominant influence than variable X_1 (independence in learning) with a value of 0.372.

INTRODUCTION

Learning independence is a part of the personality that is very necessary to support students' learning success in daily learning activities both at home and at school. The learning independence achieved by students in social studies subjects cannot be separated from the factors that influence it. The success of the learning process is influenced by internal and external factors of the students. Internal factors in question are factors that come from within the student, including student intelligence, motivation, interest, independence, time management, attitude and talent. Meanwhile, external factors are meant from outside the student, namely the family environment, community environment and the environment. school. One of the factors that need to be considered to achieve learning outcomes is learning independence. According to Yuliani Sujiono in Yamin, H. Martinis and Jamilah Sabri Sanan, (2023:66) "Independent learning is an effort made and intended to train students to solve their problems.

Based on the researcher's experience when implementing the Field Experience Practice Program (PPL), the social studies learning process at SMP Negeri 5, the researcher saw that the majority of students still relied on their friends to do the assignments given by the teacher, they had to be reminded first to study, if they were given homework (homework).), students tend to be happier doing it at school and more often copy their friends' work. Apart from that, students must be reminded first to learn and lack the initiative or inner will to make better use of learning resources available at school and outside school. They lack confidence in expressing their own opinions, and they easily get bored while learning. Students are more indifferent when they encounter questions they don't understand.

Apart from learning independence, time management also plays an important role in maximally improving student learning outcomes. Time management is very necessary in the learning process so that learning activities can run well. Time management is managing one's time by first identifying needs and desires, then managing other interests. With time management, someone can plan and use time effectively and efficiently so that they don't waste time in their life. Students' use of time can be seen through their ability in time management, namely planning and managing their time. Students who have good time management will certainly use their time well and produce good results, such as learning outcomes that meet expectations and they will not waste time in vain and make the best use of their time.

According to Dwi (2011: 7), time management is planning, organizing, mobilizing and monitoring time productivity. Time is a performance resource. Resources that must be managed so that a task can be carried out effectively and efficiently.

Based on the researcher's experience during practical field experience carried out at SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar, in reality many students consider time to be trivial, especially in the learning process, they often waste their free time in vain instead of studying things that are not important, for example not listening to the teacher. when explaining, playing after school and most often found students who spend their time playing, chatting, even just sitting with their peers. Not a few of them, if they get homework given by the teacher, will do their homework at school by copying their classmates' homework, because they often take their free time for

granted, thus hampering the learning process which will automatically cause their learning results to decline.

Learning outcomes function to see the extent to which students can master learning after following the teaching and learning process which is marked by numbers, letters or symbols agreed upon by the education provider.

In general, the teaching and learning process is said to be successful if the student's learning outcomes are able to achieve and pass the Minimum Requirements Criteria (KKM) that have been determined by the school.

You can see below a table of the percentage of daily test scores in class VIII of SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siatar which has been determined by the school, and it is known that the KKM for social science subjects is 70. For more details, see the table below.

Table 1.1. Mark Test Class Daily VII Social Sciences

No	Class	Amount Student	Mark UAS			
			<70	%	>70	%
1	VIII-1	32	9	28%	23	67%
2	VIII-2	30	9	30%	21	67%
3	VIII-3	31	7	22%	24	72%
4	VIII-4	31	5	16%	26	81%
5	VIII-5	32	5	15%	27	81%
6	VIII-6	30	6	20%	24	78%
	Total	186	41		145	

Source: list of daily test scores for QA 2022/2023)

In table 1.1 above it can be seen that student learning outcomes are still not optimal. There was a deviation between expectations and reality. Of the 186 class VIII students, it was hoped that 90% of class VIII students for social studies subjects would achieve a KKM score of 70, namely 167 students, but in reality what happened was seen from the learning results obtained, there were only 145 class VIII students who achieving the KKM score for social studies subjects, this is said to be far from expectations.

Therefore, in this research, independent learning and time management are important factors for optimally improving student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar.

Based on the background above, the author is interested in conducting research with the title " **The Influence of Learning Independence and Time Management on The Sciences Learning Outcomes of Class VIII Students of SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar**"

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Learning Independence

In the world of education, it is no longer strange to hear the word independent learning. Based on national education goals, one of the goals of education which is an important potential to develop in humans is independence. Because independence is an ability related to the ability to make decisions regarding everything related to individual activities and needs. The term "independence" in learning consists of two syllables, namely independence and learning. The term "independence" comes from the basic word "diri" which has the prefix "ke" and the suffix "an", then forms a state word or noun. Because independence comes from the word "self", the discussion about independence cannot be separated from the discussion about the development of the self itself, which in concept is called the term self, because the self is the essence of independence.

According to Aini (2012: 54) "Learning Independence is a learning activity carried out by students based on their own abilities and having high self-confidence in completing their assignments." Furthermore, according to Yuliani Sujiono in Yamin, H. Martinis and Jamilah Sabri Sanan, (2023:66) "Independent learning is an effort made and intended to train students in solving problems. Independence is very closely related to children as individuals who have a self-concept, self-esteem and self-regulation.

It can be concluded that independent learning is a learning activity based on encouragement from students without relying on the help of other people, whether from friends, teachers or even parents, in achieving their learning goals. Students have a high sense of willingness and confidence in learning as well carry out tasks to achieve learning goals, master the material or knowledge well with their own awareness and students can apply their knowledge in solving problems in everyday life.

Independence does not mean forgetting the teacher's role as a distributor of knowledge to students. Here it is emphasized that students must have high learning independence. Students may ask questions if they do not understand the material taught by the teacher, and of course they must be more active and look for other learning resources in solving problems related to the learning material discussed. Independent students always have the drive within themselves to continue learning and be consistent with the learning process they undertake. Students who have high learning independence will certainly influence their learning outcomes

2.2. Characteristics and Characteristics of Learning Independence

People who have independence in learning certainly have characteristics According to Jansen R.S et al in Wira Suciono (2021:5) the characteristics of people who have independent learning are as follows:

1. Have independence in the tasks given to them and make plans in managing the resources they have both internally and externally when completing tasks
2. Having a need for challenge means having a tendency to adapt to the difficulties faced when working on a task to become a challenge in something interesting and enjoyable
3. Know how to use existing resources, both from within and outside of him
4. Have persistence in learning and have certain strategies that help him learn

5. Has a tendency to make sense or meaning from what is written, read or discussed
6. Have a strategy and persistent efforts in learning

2.1.3. Factors That Influence Learning Independence

According to F Ridwan Sanjaya (2020:278), there are two factors that influence independence in learning, namely:

1. Internal Factors
Internal factors are factors that exist within oneself, including emotional factors and intellectual factors that an individual has
2. External Factors
External factors are factors that originate from outside the individual including supporting infrastructure, environment, interactions with other people, social characteristics, parenting patterns, stimulation (support from other parties, motivators and facilitators)

2.1.4. Indicators of Learning Independence

According to Sanan & Yamin in Muhammad Sobri (2020: 14-15) there are several indicators that independent children have, including:

1. Believe in your own abilities
2. Have motivation and encouragement to act from within the individual
3. Creative and innovative
4. Take responsibility or accept the consequences for the risks of their actions
5. Don't depend on other people (try not to need other people's help to remain independent)

2.2. Time Management

Time management is a very useful skill, managing time well means managing life well. In English, management comes from the word to manage which means to arrange, take care of, implement, and manage. Basically, proper time management includes the ability to prioritize tasks correctly, make the right schedule, and avoid procrastination. In the Big Indonesian Dictionary, time is the entire series of moments when a process, creation, or situation exists or takes place. Time management is something that can organize all daily activities to be more effective and efficient, including studying.

According to Dwi (2011: 7), time management is planning, organizing, mobilizing and monitoring time productivity. Time is a performance resource. Resources that must be managed so that a task can be carried out effectively and efficiently. Meanwhile, according to Widyawati in Hesri Mintowati (2022: 34), "Time management is the ability to prioritize, schedule and carry out individual responsibilities for the individual's own satisfaction."

2.2.2. Factors That Influence Study Time

Each individual's time management is different from other individuals. According to Hoffer (2016:30) explains that the factors that can influence student time management are:

1. Self-strengthening
Self-strengthening is an important thing in a person's life. The better a person's self-management, the better they will be able to manage their time

2. Motivation
Someone who has high self-motivation will also have good time management skills
3. Achievement of goals
Someone who tries to achieve their goals seriously can manage their time well. Rahardi in Hurhidayati (2016: 27) explains several factors that influence student time management, including:
 - a) Internal factors that make mistakes
 - b) Life outlook factor (life way)
 - c) School environmental factors

2.2.3. Strategies to Activate and Make Study Time Efficient

Every schedule that has been made needs further evaluation to identify the things that take up the most time and create alternatives or solutions to reduce or replace activities that are felt to thwart the learning targets that have been determined. According to Gie in Nurhidayanti (2016:27) there are four techniques for using time for time management for studying, namely:

1. Students should determine the subjects they will study every day, at least two or four subjects every day
2. Sort the time to study the two or four subjects according to difficulty and ease which is related to when students reach the best time to study.
3. Arrange the length of the study period as best as possible so that it is not too short or too long, how long the study period should be applied by the individual concerned.
4. Study intensively to master a subject.

2.2.4. Determining Study Time

Before setting study time, we must determine how much time is available for study each day. According to Slameto (2010:83) the way to make the best schedule is:

1. Calculate time every day for your needs needs for sleeping, studying, eating, exercising and so on.
2. Investigate and determine the times available each day
3. Plan the use of learning by determining the types of subjects and the order in which they must be studied
4. Investigate which times can be used to study with the best results. Once that time is known, it is then used to study lessons that are considered difficult. Lessons that are considered easy to learn during other study hours
5. Save time, every student should not hesitate to start work, including studying.

According to Slameto (2010:83) also adds another way to make a schedule as follows:

1. Sleep: around 8 hours
2. Eating, bathing, exercising: around 3 hours
3. Personal matters and others: around 2 hours
4. The rest (a, b, c) for studying: around 11 hours

2.2.5. Time Management Indicator

According to Akintson in Nika Sintesa (1994: 40) says that indicators in time management include:

1. Setting goals
The main part of time management is setting goals for the things you want to achieve
2. Set priorities
Tasks have different characteristics of importance or urgency. Therefore, in its implementation, priorities must be determined among various activities
3. Make a schedule
A schedule is a list of activities carried out based on time in a period, namely making a list of things that must be done, allocate the time needed, plan rest time, use a planner or other reminder source
4. Assertive
Assertiveness can be interpreted as a firm action to say no or refuse a request or task from another person in a positive way
5. Avoid procrastination
Delays in carrying out tasks can result in failure to complete work on time and disrupt the goals that have been set
6. Minimize wasted time
Waste of time includes all activities that take up time and do not provide maximum benefits

2.3. Learning outcomes

According to Sudjana in Haryanto (2022:28) "Learning outcomes are the abilities that students have after they receive learning experiences." According to Purwanto in Umi Kulsum (2023:10) "learning outcomes are the results obtained by students after carrying out learning activities, in the form of affective, cognitive and psychomotor".

Based on several opinions above, learning outcomes can be interpreted as the results achieved by students in learning, which shows the level of students' abilities in following the learning program within a certain time according to the predetermined curriculum. These learning outcomes are often reflected as grades (learning outcomes) which determine whether students are successful in learning

2.3.2. Types of Learning Outcomes

According to Bloom in Ibnu Mahtumi et al (2022:14-17) classifies the types of learning outcomes as follows:

1. Cognitive Domain
The cognitive domain relates to intellectuals which consists of 6 aspects, namely knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, synthesis, evaluation
2. Affective Domain
In the affective realm here we are concerned with attitudes and values. The type of affective learning outcomes appears in students in various behaviors such as attention to lessons, discipline, motivation to learn, respect for teachers, study habits, and social relationships.
3. The psychomotor domain appears in the form of individual skills and ability to act

2.3.3. Factors that Influence Learning Outcomes

According to Sabri in Sujarwanto (2022:33) there are two factors that influence learning outcomes, namely:

1. Internal factors

Internal factors or factors that originate from within the student. These factors can be classified into two, namely physiological factors and psychological factors. The category of physiological factors includes the student's physical condition, the condition of the five senses. The categories of psychological factors are the ability to perceive, remember, think and have basic knowledge abilities

2. External factors

Factors originating from outside the student. Classified into two, namely environmental factors and instrumental factors. The environmental factors category is the natural environment such as temperature, humidity in the air where the madrasah is located and so on. Second, socio-cultural environmental factors such as values and norms; Language; traditions and customs; religion and belief. The instrumental factor category includes classroom buildings or physical facilities, learning facilities or tools, learning media, teachers, and curriculum or lesson materials and learning strategies.

2.3.4. Learning Outcome Indicators

According to Lasmana Aan in Ibnu Mahtumi, et al (2022:17-19) the learning outcome indicators are as follows:

1. Cognitive (creative domain) includes:
 - a. Observation means being able to show, compare and connect.
 - b. Memory, meaning it can show again.
 - c. Understanding, meaning being able to explain and interpret in your own language.
 - d. Application/application, meaning providing the right example.
 - e. Analysis (careful examination and sorting), means the activity of describing and classifying.
 - f. Synthesis (making a new and complete alloy), means being able to connect materials and make them whole.
2. Affective (taste domain) includes:
 - a. Acceptance, meaning being able to show an attitude of acceptance and rejection.
 - b. Welcome means willingness to participate and take advantage.
 - c. Appreciation (appreciative attitude), means considering it important, useful, beautiful, harmonious, admiring.
 - d. Internalization (deepening), meaning following, believing, and denying.
 - e. Characterization (perception), meaning that indicators can be institutionalized or eliminated, manifested in personal and daily behavior.

2.5. Conceptual framework

Students' independent attitude is one of the internal factors that can improve learning outcomes. Student independence is a form of student freedom to take high initiative, internal self-control, freedom of expression, innovation and self-confidence. Basically, the success of a school is seen from the learning outcomes obtained by students within a certain period of time. Learning outcomes are students' abilities obtained after learning activities which are indicated by grades, numbers or letters given by the social studies teacher. However, sometimes students' social studies

learning outcomes are still less than expected due to various factors that influence them. Learning outcomes are influenced by internal and external factors.

The internal factors in question come from within the students, namely, among others, students' intelligence, interests, motivation, independence, attitudes and talents. Meanwhile, external factors come from outside the students, namely the family environment, community environment, school environment. There are several factors that influence students' unsatisfactory learning outcomes, namely learning independence and time management. Independent learning is a learning activity that occurs because of the urge to master knowledge or competence without depending on other people, which arises from within the student without orders from other people. Student learning independence is very necessary in the teaching and learning process, even for these students. Apart from learning independence, there is also time management.

Time management is how a person is able to divide time by making plans and schedules of activities to utilize time effectively and efficiently to achieve goals. Students must be able to make the most of their 24 hours without wasting it. Students should spend more time studying. Students must be able to prioritize their main goals and avoid delays in carrying out assignments. Having independent learning and time management applied by students in studying will certainly improve student learning outcomes. Independent learning will make students learn and management teaches students how important it is to spend time studying and respecting time because of their obligations as students. Based on the description that has been stated, learning independence and time management are believed to influence learning outcomes.

Figure 2.1. conceptual framework

METHODS

This research uses quantitative research with quantitative descriptive data analysis. Class VIII students of SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar with a total of 186 students constitute the population in this study. Sampling in this study used the proportional allocation formula technique. Using sampling techniques in this research, there were 127 people consisting of classes VIII-1, VIII-2, VIII-3, VIII-4, VIII-5 and VIII-6. Data collection techniques use questionnaires and documentation. The hypothesis making technique uses multiple linear regression analysis.

RESULTS

The results of this research show that there is an influence of learning independence and time management on learning outcomes in social studies subjects. proven by the following calculation results

Table 4.1 T Test Results

Model	Coefficients ^a				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	29.426	6.963		4.226	.000
Independence	.372	.094	.323	3.954	.000
Time Management	.373	.097	.315	3.857	.000

a. Dependent Variable : Learning outcomes

(Source: Research results, 2023 (Processed Data))

The results of this study show that: 1) There is a positive and significant influence of learning independence on student learning outcomes, seen from the significance value in the t test results of $0.000 < 0.05$, and the t test where the calculated t value of learning independence is $(3.954) > t$ table (1.65694) which means that this variable is significant. 2) There is a positive and significant influence of time management on student learning outcomes, seen from the t test where the calculated t value of time management is $(3.857) > t$ table (1.65694) which means that this variable is significant.

Tabel 4.2 F Test Results

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1920,882	2	960,441	23,755	,000 ^b
	Residual	5013.544	124	40,432		
	Total	6934.425	126			

a. Dependent Variable: Learning Outcomes

b. Predictors: (Constant), Time Management, Independence

(Source: Research results, 2023 (Processed Data))

Learning independence and time management together influence learning outcomes, seen from the F test where the calculated F value is (23.755) > table F value (3.067).

Tabel 4.3 Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Durbin-Watson
1	.526 ^a	.277	.265	6.359	.277	

a. Predictors: (Constant), Time Management, Independence

b. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

The R square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.277, which means that 27.7% of the learning independence and time management variables influence student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 72.3% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research. The regression value is 1920.882, while the residual value is 5013.544, which means there are other factors that influence learning outcomes but were not examined in this study, namely 5013.544.

(Source: Research results, 2023 (Processed Data))

Table 4.4 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	29.426	6.963		4.226	.000
Independence	.372	.094	.323	3.954	.000
Time Management	.373	.097	.315	3.857	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Learning outcomes

The regression value is 1920.882, while the residual value is 5013.544, which means there are other factors that influence learning outcomes but were not studied in this study, namely 5013.544. The results of the multiple regression analysis test are $Y = 29.426 + 0.372X_1 + 0.373X_2$, which means that variable X_2 (time management) with a value of 0.373 has a more dominant influence than variable X_1 (independence in learning) with a value of 0.372.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the research and discussion described in the previous chapter, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. There is a positive and significant influence of learning independence on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of learning independence (3.954) < t table value (1.65694) which means this variable is significant.
2. There is a positive and significant influence of time management on learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of time management (3.857) > t table (1.65694) which means this variable is significant.
3. Learning independence and time management together influence learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the F test where the Fcount value (23.755) > Ftable value (3.0675). The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.277, which means that 27.7% of the learning independence and time management variables influence student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 5 Pematang Siantar and the remaining 79.8% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

Recommendations

The suggestions in this research are:

1. For future researchers who wish to research or develop the same research, the author suggests considering variations in the samples to be studied and of course other variables such as learning interest and learning environment

which were not examined in this research, in order to provide more accurate predictions. on student learning outcomes.

2. For students, it is recommended to improve social studies learning outcomes by cultivating an attitude of independent learning and good time management in students, by accustoming themselves to be able to learn on their own, not relying on friends and taking the initiative in looking for learning resources and asking the teacher if facing difficulties in learning. In this case, students' time management must prioritize study and school matters most importantly. So by instilling this attitude it can improve student learning outcomes.
3. For social studies teachers as input to be able to pay more attention and direct students in learning, so that students can be independent and not depend on their peers, and always prioritize time for studying rather than wasting time on things that are not important.

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